

DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE OF ANISOTROPIC HOLLOW BEAM USING THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

With the development of processing technology of high performance thermoplastic polymers, light-weight structural applications for fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites are expanding rapidly in a number of sectors because thermoplastic composites have potential to achieve high-cycle and low-cost manufacturing and high recyclability in contrast to thermosetting composites [1,2]. Above all, polypropylene (PP), by itself or with other polymers, has been widely applied to automotive structural members such as bumper faces and interior parts because of high toughness and simple fabrication techniques [1].

A new type of thermoplastic composite materials, carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene (CF/PP) which is composed of surface treated carbon fiber (TR50S provided by Mitsubishi Rayon) and maleic-acid modified polypropylene (developed by TOYOBO) [3,4], has been developed for the purpose of applying to automobile frame structures in order to achieve significant reduction of vehicle weight. In addition, a high-cycle manufacturing technology by compression molding process to make effective use of high formability of the developed CF/PP has also been developed.

In this study, we focus on the mechanical behavior of the developed CF/PP, which can compose at least two types of fiber reinforced configurations. One is a laminated constitution of chopped tapes deposited at random in in-plane pattern and the other is a unidirectional laminate. We introduce the finite element analysis (FEA) by taking into consideration hybrid composition of unidirectional CF/PP laminate (UD laminate) and chopped tapes CF/PP laminate (CTT laminate), which leads to a new design approach of anisotropic hollow beam which satisfies both of high stiffness and high impact-absorbing.

2 Material specification

2.1 Specimen manufacture

A compression molding of thermoplastic composites is appropriate for high-speed manufacture [5,6]. Fig.1 shows a molding process from a roll of the prepreg tape with the polypropylene impregnated into a continuous unidirectional bundle of the carbon fibers to a CTT laminate and a specimen. The specimen is cut from a CTT laminate, in which a lot of chopped CF/PP tapes are deposited at random in in-plane pattern. In this process, the pre-consolidated plate of chopped tapes is heated up to about 210 °C in a infrared heater, and right after that, the heated plate is delivered to and placed on the lower mold set on the press machine, and next, cooled down and compressive pressed around 120 °C with a pressure of 18MPa. Table.1 shows each composition of CTT laminate or UD laminate respectively. From mechanical aspect, the UD laminate has an orthotropic property and the CTT laminate has an in-plane isotropic property.

Fig.1 Molding process of CTT laminate and specimen.

Table.1 Composition of CTT and UD laminates.

	CTT laminate	UD laminate
Carbon Fiber	TR50S	TR50S
Volume Fraction	50%	50%
Tape size	Length: 35mm Width: 15mm	(Continuous)
Matrix	Acid modified polypropylene	Acid modified polypropylene
Mechanical property	In-plane isotropic	Orthotropic

Fig.2 Static 3-point-bending test.

Fig.3 Strain-stress curves of CTT and CF-SMC.

2.2 Static 3-point-bending test

As shown in Fig.2, the strain-stress relationships of the developed CF/PP were examined by static 3-point-bending test using universal testing machine (SHIMADZU AGS-5kNX) which can record a load-deflection curve. The test results are shown in Fig.3. Here, for comparison, the graph plots both of strain-stress curves of CTT and UD laminate, whose material main properties are listed in Table.1. From test result, it was found that the flexural fracture behavior of CTT is clearly ductile different from that of thermosetting composites, for example, CF-SMC which has the same volume fraction of the same carbon fiber but uses vinyl ester as a matrix [7]. On

the other hand, the stiffness and strength of CTT are lower than those of UD laminate, but the stress of CTT declines gradually with the strain increasing after the fracture start. In other words, using CTT as a structural material performs a potential of higher fracture-energy-absorbing.

3 Equivalent stiffness design by classical analysis

In case of applying the developed CF/PP, whose density is about 1.35g/cm^3 and whose volume fraction of carbon fiber is 0.5, to a hollow beam as a representative of the structural frames, the flexural stiffness of a CF/PP hollow beam should be equal to or more than a replaced steel hollow beam.

In Fig.4, the relationships of carbon fiber volume fraction and weight reduction ratio of hollow beam are indicated in both cases of only CTT and only UD. Here, the tensile modulus of carbon fiber was defined as 240GPa and the isotropic elastic modulus of CTT was estimated at about one third of the fiber directional elastic modulus of UD laminate by the rule of mixtures [8]. If our target of the weight ratio is a half of steel manufacture, a CF/PP hollow beam has to be anisotropic in longitudinal direction to make use of the composite characteristics. Fig.5 explains an example that the longitudinal elastic modulus of the applied material should be 77GPa by using classical analysis. From these aspects, an applicable anisotropic design, which combines the best properties of CTT and UD, should be installed to a significant lightweight hollow beam.

Fig.4 Weight reduction ratio of CF/PP hollow beam to steel hollow beam.

	Steel hollow beam	CF/PP hollow beam	Ratio to Steel
Elastic Modulus (E)	$E_s = 200\text{GPa}$	$E_c = 77\text{GPa}$ ($V_f=0.5$)	1/2.6
Thickness (t)		2.9	
Outside size (h)	h	h	1
Volume ($V \propto t$)	v	2.9v	2.9
Second moment of area ($h=50, t=1$)	$I_s = \frac{h^4 - (h - 2t)^4}{12} = 78500$	$I_c = \frac{h^4 - (h - 2 \cdot 2.9t)^4}{12} = 203000$	2.6/1 ($\cong 203000/78500$)
Flexural stiffness	$E_s I_s$	$E_c I_c (=1/2.6 * E_s * 2.6/1 * I_s)$	1
Deformation ($\delta \propto P/EI$)		1 same flexural performance	
Density (ρ)	7.8	1.35	1/5.8
Weight (W)	7.8v	1.35*2.9v	1/2

Fig. 5 Weight reduction analysis for hollow beam with rectangular section

4 Design of a CF/PP hollow beam

4.1 FEA model

The anisotropic CF/PP hollow beam with flange was designed by using the finite element analysis (FEA) model as shown in Fig.6. The geometries and mesh elements were created in Altair Hypermesh 11.0. MAT25 was used as material property of a laminar ply for the laminated shell element and MAT36 was used as material property of matrix between laminated plies for elastic-plastic-piecewise-linear material. And, for the pre-processing in Hypermesh 11.0, PROP17 was used as laminated shell element for stacking multi plies defined by MAT25. Based on the rule of mixtures [8], CTT and UD properties assigned to each ply of the upper, lower and side plate of the hollow beam were defined in MAT25 as indicated Table.2. Each shell element as a ply of CTT has in-plane isotropic property and each shell element as a ply of UD has orthotropic property. And, the failure behavior of all elements was defined to comply with Tsai-Wu criterion. And, the stress-strain relationship of a layer between laminated plies as matrix was defined as a user-defined curve as Fig.7 indicates.

The FEA model demonstrated the 3-point-bending test and was compared to the experimental results. For saving the computation time, 1/4 model was constructed as shown in Fig.6. In this model, the indenter and support had rigid body property. And, the indenter was assigned with a constant speed in the vertical direction and detected the reactive force influenced by the deformation of the hollow beam. Those loading and boundary conditions as well as the meshing properties were imported to Altair RADIOSS 11.0 for an explicit analysis.

Fig.6 FEA 1/4 model of 3-point-bending test.

Table.2 Material properties of CTT and UD

Material properties		CTT	UD
Elastic modulus (GPa)	E_1	35	105
	E_2	35	2.9
	E_3	2.9	2.9
	G_{12}	13.5	1.1
	G_{13}	1.0	1.1
	G_{23}	1.0	0.9
Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	0.3	0.26
	ν_{13}	0.59	0.26
	ν_{23}	0.59	0.59

Fig.7 Elastic plastic piecewise property of PP matrix

4.2 Comparison to experiment result

For comparison of FEA result to experimental result, a CTT beam with a hat-section whose thickness is 2.2mm was manufactured in the same molding process as Fig.1 shows, where the shape of pressing mold was not a plate but a hat-channel [5]. And next, a hat-channel beam and a plate with the thickness 4.0mm were welded to each other by a vibration joining method. The finished part is shown in Fig.8. On another front, a steel hollow beam which has the same cross-section as the CTT hollow beam was manufactured from 780MPa-high-tensile-strength steel in order to examine a flexural behavior in a similar way (Fig.9). The thicknesses of all plates were 1.0mm and the total weight of the steel hollow beam was almost twice as the CTT hollow beam.

The 3-point-bending tests were performed by using a universal testing machine SHIMADZU AG-100kNX. The experimental results are indicated with the FEA

result in Fig.10. The graph shows the relationships of the stroke of the indenter and the vertical load detected by the indenter. As compared to the experimental relationship, it can be said that the FEA model with CTT material properties are almost valid for reproducing the experiment result, especially in initial linear deformation.

Fig.8 CTT hollow beam.

Fig.9 Steel hollow beam.

Fig.10 Comparison of experimental result and FEA result

4.3 Design for high flexural stiffness

Although the weight of the CTT hollow beam was about a half of the steel hollow beam, the flexural stiffness which was evaluated as about 1300N/mm from the linear trend of both of experimental and FEA curves in Fig.10 was decreased by more than 30% comparing to the steel hollow beam. That is because the elastic modulus of isotropic CTT was no more than 35GPa and could not attain a second moment of area to match the stiffness of the steel hollow beam as explained in classical analysis.

At that time, the thickness of the upper plate was 2.2mm and that of the lower plate was 4.0mm, so the thickness ratio of the upper plate to the lower plate was 0.55. The thicknesses of the upper plate and the lower plate can be optimized by varying the thickness ratio, improving the flexural stiffness and keeping the total weight of the hollow beam. The result of parameter study was indicated in Fig.11. The plots show the relationship between the thickness ratio and the flexural stiffness of the CTT hollow beam. From the result, in case that the thickness ratio is 2.5, that is when the upper plate has a 6.0mm thickness and the lower plate has a 2.4mm thickness, the flexural stiffness is the highest, reaching to 2000N/mm.

And next, by using the same FEA model as defined in Fig.6 and Table.2, the effect of the increasing ratio of UD plies in the upper or lower plate was investigated in a way how high the flexural stiffness of the hollow beam was improved. Fig.12 indicates the relationship between the ratio of UD plies in the upper plate and the flexural stiffness of the CF/PP hollow beam. From this result, the best ratio of UD plies in the upper plate is 0.6 and this means that the thickness of the UD plies is 3.6mm and the thickness of the CTT laminates is 2.4mm. In a similar way, in case that the ratio of the UD plies in the lower plate is from 0.4 to 0.6, the flexural stiffness of the CF/PP hollow beam is the highest as understood from Fig.13. In other words, the thicknesses of the UD plies and the CTT laminate in the lower plate which equal to each other at about 1.2mm result in the highest flexural stiffness.

From these analytic procedures using parameter studies, the shape of the hat cross-section and the ratio of UD plies to CTT laminates in the thickness of the plates can be determined for achieving the highest flexural stiffness of the CF/PP hollow beam.

Fig.11 Effect on the thickness ratio of the upper plate to the lower plate of the hollow beam.

Fig.12 Effect on the UD ratio in the upper plate.

Fig.13 Effect on the UD ratio in the lower plate.

5 Manufacturing

The shape and composition of the optimized anisotropic CF/PP hollow beam with flange was obtained by FEA model and parameter studies. In the next phase, the actual manufacturing was tested to

Fig.14 Manufacturing process of anisotropic CF/PP hollow beam.

satisfy the shape and composition. Fig.14 shows the molding process which includes a compression molding with heating and cooling system and a vibration welding. Different from the previous molding process shown in Fig.1, the pre-consolidated CTT sheet and UD sheet were heated up without pressure in the mold by heat transfer from the pressing plate with some heaters installed in the press machine. Right after reaching up to about 200 °C, the stacked sheets of CTT and UD were cooled down and compressive pressed at a pressure of 10MPa. Through these processes, a hybrid hat-section beam and a hybrid base plate with the desired thickness and ratio of UD plies were obtained. After that, by vibration welding, the hat-section beam and the base plate were combined into a CF/PP hybrid hollow beam as shown in Fig.14.

6 Verification

The 3-point-bending test was conducted to examine the relationship of stroke and load and verify how high the flexural stiffness was improved to compare to the previous CTT hollow beam. And the flexural

fracture behavior progressing during the test was investigated, comparing to the post-processing simulation in Hyperview 11.0 for the FEA result. Fig.15 shows a 3-point- bending test for the hybrid CF/PP hollow beam. And, test results in both cases of hybrid and only CTT hollow beams are indicated in Fig.16. As is clear from the initial linear slopes of two curves, the anisotropic hybrid one improves the flexural stiffness considerably in spite of almost the same weight as the CTT one.

Fig.15 3-point-bending test.

Fig.16 Experimental result of 3-point-bending test.

Fig.19 Stress distribution of the hybrid hollow beam.

Fig.20 Test piece after the 3-point-bending test

Fig.17 Comparison of FEA simulation (upper) and experimental video photo (lower).

Fig.18 Flexural behavior of experimental tests of the steel and the hybrid CF/PP with FEA result.

Fig.17 compares the deflections from side view of the post-processing simulation by the FEA model and the experimental photo recorded by a video camera at the maximum vertical load detected by the indenter. These comparisons during initial elastic deforming represents that the FEA simulation can demonstrate the total deflection of the hollow beam in the experimental behavior. The similar thing is described by comparing of the FEA and experimental curves of the hybrid CF/PP hollow beam in Fig.18.

In addition, from test results of the hybrid CF/PP one and the steel one, the hybrid one performs larger energy absorbing than the steel one because of its ductile property as well as its higher strength.

At the maximum load, the stress distribution in the longitudinal direction of the hollow beam is visualized in a contour figure as shown in Fig.19. The highest compressive stress in all mesh elements appears at a contact area of the upper plate with the indenter and the initial fracture which is expressed as a mesh break starts at the corner of the upper plate. As is also clear from the test piece after the bending test as Fig.20 shows, the compressive fracture spread from around the corner between the upper plate and the side plate, with the hollow beam compressive deforming.

7 Conclusions

In this study, an anisotropic hollow beam made from the developed CF/PP for an automobile frame structure was designed by using a FEA and manufactured by compression molding with heating and cooling system. With a FEA process, focusing on the flexural stiffness of the hollow beam obtained from a linear curve of the initial deformation, an optimal combination of the shape of hat-section and ratio of UD and CTT was worked out successfully. After verifying the flexural behavior by a static 3-point-bending test, it was confirmed that the optimized designed hybrid CF/PP hollow beam satisfied not only higher flexural stiffness but also higher energy absorbing capacity than a 780MPa-tensile-strength steel hollow beam which was the same in form but twice as heavy as the optimized designed one. And, the FEA simulation in a post-processing which can express stress distribution and damaging mode of mesh elements was valid to understand an initial fracture behavior of actual manufactured hollow beam.

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